

ISSN 2230-9071

VISION

Research Journal of Education

*There Is a World Beyond The Stars Too*****

Volume III

Number I

April 2012

Editor-in-Chief
Prof. Neshla

SRI SAI COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
BADHANI, PATHANKOT (PB.)

VISION.

Research Journal of Education

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CONTENTS

- | | | |
|---|---|-------|
| 1. Job Satisfaction in Relation to Professional Commitment and Background Factors among Primary School Teachers in Tribal Areas | Dr. Nibedita Priyadarshani | 1-15 |
| 2. Development and Evaluation of Self Learning Modules in English Grammar for Elementary School Students | Ms. Ranjana Dhamija
Dr. Neelam Dhamija | 16-23 |
| 3. Teacher -Education for Knowledge Economy | Dr. Rajeev Rattan Sharma | 24-35 |
| 4. Comparative Study of Work-Motivation among Government and Private School Teachers | Dr. Geeta Sharma
Ms. Geeta Sharma | 36-42 |
| 5. Spatial Patterns of Gender Disparities, in Literacy, in Himachal Pradesh: 2001 | Dr. Rajan Bhandari | 43-58 |
| 6. Guidance Needs of Adolescents in Relation to Their Parental Encouragement | Dr. Seema Sareen
Ms. Kirandeep Kaur | 59-67 |
| 7. Academic Achievement in Relation to Mental Health, Altruism and Socio-Economic Status of Secondary School Students | Dr. Tirath Singh
Dr. Arjinder Singh | 68-76 |
| 8. Effect of Divergent Mathematical Exercises on Creativity of Class VII Students | Dr. Yogesh Sharma | 77-85 |

SPATIAL PATTERNS OF GENDER DISPARITIES IN LITERACY IN HIMACHAL PRADESH: 2001

Dr. Rajan Bhandari*

Introduction

Literacy among males is universally found higher as compared to females particularly in developing countries of the world. Consequently disparity in male female literacy is prevalent in most of the less developed countries of the world and India is not an exception in this regard. As per Census 2001, more than three-fourths of male population was registered as literate as compared to a little more than half of total female population of India. Himachal Pradesh made remarkable progress in female literacy and scored 4th position in female literacy as compared to 5th position in overall literacy rate among all states. 76.48 percent literacy had 85.35 percent male literacy and 67.42 percent female literacy. There were large spatial variations in male and female literacy and resultant disparities in gender literacy in Himachal Pradesh.

The present study seeks to find out the spatial patterns of disparities in gender literacy in Himachal Pradesh. The difference in percentage points between male and female literacy rates can be a deceptive indicator, since it is always a small figure regardless of whether the literacy rates is very low or very high. Disparity index is a more sophisticated measure. Disparity index has been worked out on the basis of the formula suggested by Kundu and Rao, (1986) the suggested formula is in fact a modified version of Sopher's Index (1974) for measurement of disparity.

$$DS = \log (X_2/X_1) + \log (200-X_1)/(200-X_2),$$

DS= Disparity Index

$X_2 > X_1$; X_2 and X_1 are the literacy rates of the two groups between which disparity is computed. X_2 = male literacy and X_1 = female literacy.

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Disparity in Male-Female Literacy

Difference in male-female literacy is acceptable up to some extent but a large gap in literacy levels not only shows numerical gender disparity in literacy but also adjourn women's participation in socio-economic activities, health care and education of the children. Literacy is used as an indicator of the progress of women. Women's economic activity is usually confined to cooking; unpaid agricultural tasks or making cow dung cakes etc. (Sharma and Haub, 2009) and such activities are less prominent as education level goes higher. It is generally accepted that social phenomena like birth rates, death rates, infant mortality rates, and population growth rates decelerate with improvements in literacy levels. In all these cases the association is found to be stronger with female literacy than male literacy (Mukherjee, 2005). Illiterate women have high levels of fertility and mortality, poor nutritional status, low earning potential, and little autonomy within the household (Victoria and Velkoff, 1998). Importance of female literacy needs not much to be stressed.

Whereas literacy is an important determinant of economic growth (Barro, 2001) female's education may be more significant for future growth (World Bank, 2001). Literacy among females is ubiquitously low as compared to male population in India. Despite knowing and admiring the value of female literacy a little less than half of female population in India could not read and write. In 2001 census, India registered 64.84 percent literacy. With 75.26 percent male and 53.67 percent female literacy there was a difference of 21.59 percent points. In all, 24 states registered lesser whereas, 11 states experienced more than national male female difference (21.59 percent point).

In India, female literacy in Bihar, Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Arunachal Pradesh, and Rajasthan was only 33.12, 38.87, 42.22, 43.00, 43.55 and 43.85 percent, respectively as against their male literacy rates of 59.68, 67.30, 68.82, 66.60, 63.83 and 75.70 percent, respectively. All states with low female literacy experienced high male-female difference in literacy i.e. more than the national average (21.59 percent). There is a close relationship between male and female literacy and male-female difference in literacy in all states and union territories in India. The male female difference in literacy is also inversely related with both the male literacy (-0.487) and female literacy (-0.830).

In Himachal Pradesh, on an average, male-female literacy difference was 17.93 percent as compared to national average of 21.59 per cent, according to 2001 census. At district level the gender gap in male-female literacy was highest in Chamba district (27.56 percent) which also had the lowest literacy rate among both male population and female population. The male female differences in literacy by age groups increased in the upper age groups (Table 2). On the other hand the lowest difference in male-female literacy was in Hamirpur district (14.45 percent) which also displayed high literacy among males and females (Table 1). At tehsil level, Shimla Urban tehsil with 4.55 percent points had the lowest gap in male and female literacy rates whereas Saluni tehsil had a difference of 35 percent points between male and female literacy rates. Hence, differences in male-female literacy rates are high in areas where literacy level was found low.

Table 1
Himachal Pradesh: Gender Disparity in Literacy, 2001

District	Person Percent Literates	Male Percent Literates	Female Percent Literates	Literacy difference	Disparity Index
Chamba	62.91	76.41	48.85	27.56	0.2817
Kangra	80.08	87.54	73.01	14.53	0.1316
Lahul & Spiti	73.10	82.82	60.70	22.12	0.2101
Kullu	72.90	83.98	60.88	23.10	0.2186
Mandi	75.24	85.94	64.82	21.13	0.1963
Hamirpur	82.46	90.15	75.70	14.45	0.1295
Una	80.37	87.73	73.18	14.55	0.1316
Bilaspur	77.76	86.04	69.55	16.49	0.1511
Solan	76.57	84.75	66.89	17.86	0.1654
Sirmaur	70.39	79.36	60.37	18.99	0.1822
Shimla	79.12	87.19	70.07	17.12	0.1563
Kinnaur	75.20	84.30	64.40	19.90	0.1859
HP	76.48	85.35	67.42	17.93	0.1655
India	64.84	75.26	53.67	21.59	0.2161

Source: Calculated from Census of India, 2001

The index value ranged from 0.040 in Shimla Urban tehsil of Shimla district to 0.401 in Chaurah tehsil of Chamba district. Spatially the disparity was low in the peripheral tehsils

particularly in the western and southern parts of the state as these areas had experienced an early start in education, high social status of women, and a high degree of connectivity among places. The male female disparity index was high in the north western parts and in the central parts of the state as these areas had strong apathy toward female education; poor agriculture economy and almost no exposure to the outside world for a long time. In other words, the disparity index increases as the general literacy decreases. Female literacy was low in less developed areas where disparity index value was high (Map 2). The male-female literacy disparity index was low in relatively prosperous areas and high in socially and economically backward areas.

Keeping in mind, the average disparity index of 0.166 for Himachal Pradesh, three categories have been formed for the study of patterns of male-female disparity index in literacy in the state.

1. Areas with high disparity index of more than 0.2 in male-female literacy
2. Areas with low disparity index of less than 0.16 in male-female literacy
3. Areas with moderate disparity index of between 0.161 and 0.2 in male-female literacy

1. Areas with High Disparity Index of more than 0.2 in Male-Female Literacy

As many as 43 tehsils of the state recorded high index value of more than 0.2. The extent of the disparity index in this category ranges from 0.202 in Lad Bahrol to 0.401 in Chaurah tehsil. The disparity index value was extremely high in 20 tehsils in which the index value was more than 0.24. To a large extent, those areas where literacy rates were very low experienced high disparities in male female literacy. Entire Chamba, large parts of Kullu and Lahul & Spiti districts, large parts of Mandi, Shimla, and Sirmaur districts, and some parts of Solan and Bilaspur districts were in this category of high disparity index in male-female literacy.

Areas with high disparity index in male-female literacy were largest with regard to their geographic extent among all three categories as mentioned above. Such areas formed one large belt and three small pockets (Map 3). The largest belt with high disparity index extended between north-west to central part of the state and further extended to north-eastern part; covering entire Chamba district, most of Kullu and Lahul & Spiti districts, 10

tehsils of Mandi district and one each tehsil in Kangra and Kinnaur district. One small pocket with high disparity index was identified in the south-eastern part of the state covering five tehsils of Shimla district. The southern part of the state consisting of six tehsils from Sirmaur district and one from Shimla district also formed one small area with high disparity index in male-female literacy. One tehsil in Bilaspur and two tehsils in Solan along Himachal-Punjab border formed another small pocket of high disparity index.

Out of 43 tehsils with high disparity index in male-female literacy, 28 tehsils constituted the biggest almost continuous belt. All tehsils of Chamba district experienced high disparity index in male-female literacy. Chamba district had both male-female literacy less than the national average and lowest in the state. A little less than half of the total population belonged either to scheduled castes (20.04 percent) or scheduled tribes (25.25 percent) and was mostly engaged in agrarian and pastoral economy. The whole of Chamba district with the exception of Dalhousie and Chamba tehsils is entirely rural. Though, male literacy increased with time yet female literacy is still lagging behind. In Chamba district the male (92.79 percent) and female (81.94 percent) literacy rates of age group (7-19 group) were lower than the state average of 95.85 percent (male literacy) and 93.39 percent (female literacy) (Table 2). All these characteristics of the entire district resulted in low level of literacy particularly among females, which generated high male-female disparity in literacy in the entire district.

Table 2

Himachal Pradesh: Male-Female Literacy Rate by Age Groups, 2001

	Age Groups in Years									
	7 - 19		20-39		40-59		60-79		80 +	
	Male	Femal e	Male	Femal e	Male	Femal e	Male	Femal e	Male	Femal e
HIMACHAL P.	95.85	93.39	90.65	74.84	78.23	41.83	49.94	13.49	34.46	8.07
Chamba	92.79	81.94	80.52	41.04	60.17	18.86	29.32	8.17	18.70	5.77
Kangra	97.03	95.98	93.62	85.38	81.97	49.76	55.87	16.97	39.76	10.09
Lahul & Spiu	92.88	93.28	85.89	67.36	80.35	33.32	47.10	6.28	35.21	6.19
Kullu	95.95	92.14	88.98	59.99	72.25	28.93	42.31	10.23	35.80	8.63
Mandi	97.09	94.71	92.81	71.93	78.77	34.64	44.04	9.75	26.28	6.92
Hamirpur	97.65	97.67	95.90	94.74	90.81	57.69	61.58	10.60	39.02	4.67
Una	94.88	94.64	92.65	86.03	85.45	55.35	62.54	17.59	44.79	7.66
Bilaspur	96.78	95.76	94.52	83.93	81.98	42.76	41.63	7.89	23.26	5.28
Solan	94.10	92.75	89.15	71.88	76.55	38.19	47.62	14.62	33.29	9.59
Sirmaur	93.78	89.76	83.12	58.41	65.87	29.93	39.46	12.44	25.92	8.21
Shimla	96.06	94.01	91.53	75.41	80.88	44.89	54.51	18.74	44.66	13.71
Kinnaur	95.85	96.40	89.72	72.89	76.14	32.64	41.85	7.69	32.87	5.17

Source: Calculated from Census of India 2001

Areas with high disparity index in male-female literacy were largest with regard to their geographic extent among all three categories as mentioned above. Such areas formed one large belt and three small pockets (Map 3). The largest belt with high disparity index extended between north-west to central part of the state and further extended to north-eastern part; covering entire Chamba district, most of Kullu and Lahul & Spiti districts, 10 tehsils of Mandi district and one each tehsil in Kangra and Kinnaur district. One small pocket with high disparity index was identified in the south-eastern part of the state covering five tehsils of Shimla district. The southern part of the state consisting of six tehsils from Sirmaur district and one from Shimla district also formed one small area with high disparity index in male-female literacy. One tehsil in Bilaspur and two tehsils in Solan along Himachal-Punjab border formed another small pocket of high disparity index.

The tehsils of Hangrang and Spiti with high disparity index in male female literacy were beyond the Pir Panjal range and were poorly linked by road network. Due to inaccessibility these areas did not get sufficiently exposed to the outside influences resulting in low female literacy but slightly better among males. As a result of recent social awaking such gaps are on the decline but the past large base of illiterate population still drags such areas into high male female disparity index.

Sainj, Banjar, Ani and Nermand tehsils in Kullu district; Bali Chowki, Padhar, Thunag, Nihri, Aut, Karsog, Kotli, Chachyot, Jogindernagar and Lad Bharol tehsils in Mandi district were also included in this category of high disparity index in male-female literacy. These tehsils had relatively higher male literacy than female but, on an average these tehsils had low to moderate level of total literacy. Prejudices against educating females and a common belief, that females do not need any education as they merely need to look after the house and family are factors affecting female literacy adversely. Secondly, level of urbanization could be another factor having an impact on literacy levels, especially that of female literacy (Sopher, 1980).

Map 1

Map 2

Map 3

Another pocket with high disparity index in male-female literacy was situated in the southeastern part of the state covering the eastern part of Shimla district. Dodra Kwar (0.278), Chirgaon (0.277), Tikar (0.239), Rohru (0.226), and Jubbal (0.225) tehsils formed a small pocket of high disparity index in literacy. All these tehsils, Dodra Kwar, Chirgaon, Tikar, Rohru and Jubbal displayed lower female literacy ratio of 59, 60, 67, 66 and 68 per 100 literate males against the state average of 77 literate females per 100 literate males. These tehsils had moderately high literacy but low female literacy and thus resulted in high disparity index. Chairgaon and Dodra Kwar were still among backward tehsils of the state in terms of being least connected with the rest of the state. In Tikkar, Rohru and Jubbal, apple cultivation-based economy has no doubt, brought social awakening but female literacy still needs to be pushed up to come up to the level of males.

In the southern part of the state, eastern part of Sirmaur district and one tehsil of Shimla formed another pocket of high disparity index in male female literacy. Ronhat (0.250), Shalai (0.240), Renuka (0.227) and Paonta Sahib (0.205) tehsils of Sirmaur district and Cheta (0.236) in Shimla district displayed a pocket of high disparity in male female literacy. Both male and female literacy rates were low and the level of urbanization was low. None of the tehsils except Paonta Sahib had any urban population.

Ramsahar (0.251) and Nalagarh (0.221) in Solan district and Naina Devi (0.217) in Bilaspur district lying near Punjab-Himachal border, constituted another small pocket with high disparity index in male-female literacy. Naina Devi tehsil with 27.25 percent scheduled caste population and 12.73 percent scheduled tribe population, mainly of Gujjars, had low literacy both among males and females. Out migration of literates from Naina Devi influenced the tehsil's literacy level and consequently male-female disparity in literacy. Similarly Nalagarh had a very low female-male ratio of literacy (53 literate females per 100 literate males) as a result of presence of industrial towns of Baddi and Nalagarh in the neighborhood.

It may be concluded that areas with high male-female disparity index in literacy were those where overall literacy was low. These areas were inaccessible and not open to outside influences. Low degree of urbanisation, prejudices regarding female education, high percentage of scheduled caste and scheduled tribe population and late opening of educational institutions in the region were some of the factors leading to high male female

disparity in literacy.

2. Areas with Low Disparity Index of less than 0.161 in Male-Female Literacy

Areas experiencing predominantly high literacy level in the state displayed low disparity index in male female literacy i.e. less than 0.16 index value. Shimla Urban had the lowest disparity (0.0398) whereas, Mandi tehsil with 0.1588 index value, was at the other extreme. Entire Hamirpur, large parts of Una and Kangra districts, some parts of Shimla, Bilaspur, Mandi, Solan and Sirmaur districts had low disparity index in male-female literacy. Areas with a disparity index lower than 0.160 in male female literacy were consisted of two pockets. The western half of the state with low disparity index comprised Una, parts of Kangra, Mandi and Bilaspur districts. The second pocket was formed by parts of Shimla, Solan and Sirmaur districts.

The first pocket in the western half of the state had low male female disparity index in literacy. All of them had high male literacy as well as high female literacy leading to a low disparity index in literacy (Map 1 &2). This could be because of the early start of literacy for both male and females. High literacy in this region could be explained by the fact that this region is well connected by a network of roads and Pathankot-Jogindernagar railway line. The area is also well connected to the plains.

A glance at Map 3 reveals some tehsils lying in the western part of the state, showing a low disparity index of less than 0.120. The economic constraints, lack of adequate technology and scarcity of agricultural land compelled the people to move out of the country-side to urban destinations in search of jobs. This sustained migration to urban centers is perceived as promoting literacy because the migrant in turn educates other family members also.

This has resulted in high male and female literacy and consequently low disparity index in male female literacy. Another factor for lower disparity in male-female literacy is that these tehsils were a part of Punjab state till the reorganization of the state in 1966. All tehsils which were formerly a part of Punjab state exhibited high male and female literacy rates, were well connected, economically developed and open to outside influences. With an early

start of education the illiterate base is small and whatever exists is in the old age group. High literacy level could sustain recruitment into military services. High male literacy in these areas is attributed to military training and diffusion of the idea that literacy makes economic advancement possible (Gosal, 1964, p.275).

Another pocket with low disparity index was in the southern part of the state comprising areas with high literacy level. Shimla Urban (0.040), Junga (0.128), Shimla Rural (0.132), Theog (0.149) and Chaupal (0.151) in Shimla district; Solan (0.105), Kandaghat (0.142) and Kasauli (0.126) in Solan district; Rajgarh (0.120), Nahan (0.146) and Nohra (0.149) in Sirmaur district all had low disparity index in male female literacy.

Shimla Urban tehsil and Solan tehsil displayed the lowest disparity index in male-female literacy in the entire state. Shimla town was the summer capital of India during the British period and also Punjab Government after independence. Since then it flourished as an administrative, educational and commercial centre. Shimla is the only class I town in Himachal Pradesh and has positively influenced the literacy levels of the surrounding areas making Shimla tehsil the most literate tehsil in the state. Solan tehsil has 42.76 percent population living in urban areas. Participation of both males and females in service sector has a significant role in narrowing down the disparity index. Sopher (1980) in his study has found that literacy increases and sex disparity in literacy rates decreases in a fairly even progression by urban settlement size in India. This statement stands proven in case of Solan and Shimla tehsils also where literacy is high because urbanisation is high.

Thus, the low disparity index was associated with areas of high level of literacy which represents male as well as female population with high literacy rate. The low disparity index in male female literacy in Himachal Pradesh is basically a product of high urbanization, good connectivity, early start of education and awareness among females.

3. Areas with Moderate Disparity Index of between 0.161 and 0.2 in Male-Female Literacy

Those areas where index value was found between 0.161 and 0.200 have been placed in the category of moderate disparity in male-female literacy. The category included 26 tehsils at least one each from all districts of the state other than Chamba and Hamirpur districts.

Chamba and Hamirpur districts were entirely displaying highest and lowest disparity index in literacy and had none of the tehsils in this category. Areas with moderate disparity index were situated in between areas of high and areas of low disparity index. There was one large belt and two pockets and some isolated tehsils with moderate disparity index in male female literacy.

In Kinnaur Solan belt, 15 tehsils constituted a longitudinal belt of moderate disparity index starting from Ramsahars in Solan district to Poo in Kinnaur district, more or less along the Satluj River. With few exceptions, males had high literacy and females had moderate level of literacy in this belt.

Kangra-Mandi pocket consisted of Khundian (0.173), Jaisinghpur (0.163) and Baroh (0.161) in Kangra district; and Dharampur (0.196) and Sandhol (0.178) in Mandi District. All these tehsils except Khundia tehsil experienced high male-female literacy. Khundia tehsil is one of the backward tehsils with moderate level of literacy among both males and females. Interestingly, all these tehsils experienced literate ratio higher than the state average. Jaisinghpur had an exception of 101 literate females per 100 literate males; other tehsils also showed high value: Khundian (85), Dharampur (86), Baroh (92) and Sandhol (94). High literacy ratio in Jaisinghpur is an outcome of out migration of male population and secondly, due to high female literacy.

Lahul (0.173) and Manali (0.185) in the north and Pachhad (0.169) and Dadahu (0.193) in the southern part of state were identified as two small pockets with moderate disparity index in male female literacy. Haroli (0.183) in Una district and Nerua (0.186) in Shimla district were isolated tehsils with moderate disparity index in male female literacy.

In brief, areas with moderate disparity index were surrounded either by high disparity areas or by low disparity areas. Such areas were scattered in the entire state both in areas with high literacy as well as low literacy

Conclusion

Himachal Pradesh despite having achieved a better position in terms of literacy has large spatial variations particularly in female literacy. After its formation, the state has made substantial development in the field of communication, transportation, electrification of the

far flung areas, and rapid growth of secondary and tertiary sectors which transformed lives in rural areas. Since the state is the least urbanized state in India, development in different spheres of life assumed special importance for improving literacy and to promote literacy particularly at elementary level, the state government worked in the direction of providing educational facilities to cater to the needs of maximum number of people living in the area. Government of India started an extensive programme to eliminate illiteracy by introducing Universalization of Elementary Education in the last decade of the 20th century. As a result of such programmes the state experienced a high literacy level in the young age group.

The largest belt with high disparity index extended between north-west to central parts of the state and further extended to north-eastern part. Another pocket of high disparity index in male-female literacy was in the southern part of the state. The region with high disparity in male female literacy was mainly the interior part of the state bounded by mountains. Low degree of urbanisation, prejudices regarding female education, high percentage of scheduled caste and scheduled tribe population and late opening of educational institutions in the region were some of the factors leading to high male female disparity in literacy.

Areas experiencing predominantly high literacy level in the state displayed low disparity index in male female literacy. Areas with a disparity index of less than 0.16 in male female literacy were consisted of two pockets. The western half of the state comprised of Una, parts of Kangra, Mandi and Bilaspur districts formed the first pocket with low disparity index in male female literacy. The second pocket was formed by parts of Shimla, Solan and Sirmaur districts. The low disparity index in male female literacy in Himachal Pradesh is basically a product of high urbanization, good connectivity, early start of education, awareness among females and out migration for service in other states.

Himachal Pradesh has yet to go a long way to bridge the gap between male-female but to reduce the gap in male-female literacy, introduction of more adult literacy centers may be appreciated deeply.

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